

Thiourea and its Organic Derivatives. Part II. Oxidimetric Determination with Iodine Monochloride

Balwant Singh, Balbir Chand Verma and M. S. Saran

Iodine monochloride has been used as a redox reagent for the determination of thiourea and its several alkyl and aryl derivatives, visually and by potentiometric titration.

The thioureas are oxidised to the corresponding disulphides in sulphuric acid medium with a single electron change.

Among the various reagents used for the estimation of thiourea are silver nitrate, copper sulphate, cadmium acetate, mercuric and potassium iodides, potassium bromate, chloramine-T, mercuric nitrate, bromine, potassium metaperiodate, potassium ferricyanide, selenious acid, iodine, sodium nitrite, and potassium iodate. Grover and Mehrotra¹ reported that thiourea was oxidised to urca and sulphate by hypiodite and to sulphate, carbonate, and nitrogen by hypobromite in alkaline solutions. Bayer and Posgay² determined thiourea by titrating its acetic acid solution with 0.1N perchloric acid (in anhydrous glacial acetic acid) in presence of mercuric acetate using gentian violet as an indicator. Alicino³ used acetic acid solutions of crystal violet and quinaldine red as indicators in the above titration. Budesinsky *et al.*⁴ determined thiourea and some of its derivatives by heating them with cadmium-EDTA complex, when cadmium sulphide was precipitated quantitatively. The precipitated cadmium sulphide was removed and the liberated EDTA was titrated with calcium chloride in presence of methyl thymol blue as an indicator. Wronski⁵ titrated thiourea and semicarbazide hydrochloride in aqueous or ethanolic solution with tris-(acetoxymercuri)aniline solution in presence of perchloric acid using *p*-dimethylaminobenzylidenerhodanine as an indicator.

Preisler and Berger⁶ found oxidation-reduction potential of thiourea—formamidine disulphide system:

to be 0.420 volts in 0.05 to 1N-HCl. They stated that this system was analogous to thiol—disulphide system:

1. *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1958, **160**, 287.
2. *Naturwiss.*, 1958, **45**, 185.
3. *Microchem. J.*, 1960, **4**, 551.
4. *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1960, **25**, 456.
5. *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1960, **174**, 3.
6. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 332.

Mahr⁷ determined thiourea in sulphuric acid medium by titrating it with standard bromate-bromide solution in presence of small amounts of potassium iodide and starch. The end point was marked by appearance of a blue colour when thiourea was oxidised to formamidine disulphide. Banerjee⁸ determined thiourea in presence of varied amounts of mercuric chloride by using Mahr's method in a modified form. Werner⁹ estimated thiourea by oxidising it to formamidine disulphide with excess of selenious acid and determining the unchanged excess of thiourea iodometrically.

Cihalik and Ruzicka¹⁰ carried out a potentiometric titration of thiourea with iodine monochloride and reported that thiourea was oxidised to formamidine disulphide in neutral to strongly acidic solutions.

No systematic study has so far been made to estimate organic derivatives of thiourea by oxidimetric methods. In the present study an attempt has been made to oxidise thiourea and some of its alkyl and aryl derivatives to their corresponding disulphides in sulphuric acid medium using iodine monochloride as a redox reagent.

EXPERIMENTAL

The organic derivatives of thiourea were prepared by well-known methods and purified by repeated crystallisations from suitable solvents.

Potassium iodate (A.R.) (1.7834 g.) and potassium iodide (A.R.) (2.7668 g.) were dissolved in water (250 ml) and the solutions mixed with HCl (conc., 250 ml) to prepare iodine monochloride solution. A small amount of chloroform was added to the solution which was then titrated with either iodate or iodide, as needed, until the organic layer remained faintly violet after shaking. Finally volume of the solution was made to one litre with 5*N*-HCl and it was standardised by an iodometric method.

A known weight (10 to 55 mg.) of each compound was taken in a titration flask. In case of thiourea and its alkyl derivatives, sufficient water and enough of H₂SO₄ or HCl to keep normality of the solution at 1*N* were added. Each aryl derivative of thiourea (10 to 55 mg.) was dissolved in 18*N*-H₂SO₄ (10 to 15 ml) and sufficient water (40 to 90 ml) was added to keep normality of the solution at 2.5 to 3.5*N*. The solution in each case was cooled to room temperature and titrated with standard (*N*/20) iodine monochloride. End point in each titration was detected visually as well as potentiometrically. In visual titrations, amylose was used as an indicator and the solution acquired a blue colour at the end point.

In potentiometric method, a platinum wire, immersed in the solution to be titrated, was used as an oxidation-reduction electrode and this was coupled with a saturated calomel electrode. The solution was kept stirred by a mechanical stirrer during the titration. Progress of the reaction was studied with a Mullard potentiometer. At the equivalence point there was a sharp jump in potential in each titration. Potentiometric titrations were performed with different amounts of each compound (Fig. 1).

7. *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1939, **117**, 81.

8. *This Journal*, 1959, **36**, 449.

9. *Analyst*, 1940, **65**, 286.

10. *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1956, **21**, 262.

From the volume of standard (*N*/20) iodine monochloride solution used corresponding to the end point in each titration, the amounts of thiourea and each of its organic derivatives have been calculated. Some typical results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Derivatives.	Weight of the compound.			
	Visual method.		Potentiometric method.	
	Taken.	Found.	Taken.	Found.
$\text{NH}_2\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{NH}_2$	0.0304 g.	0.0304 g.	0.0266 g.	0.0265 g.
	0.0456	0.0455	0.0457	0.0455
$\text{CH}_3\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{NH}_2$	0.0355	0.0353	0.0146	0.0145
	0.0453	0.0451	0.0499	0.0499
$\text{CH}_3\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{NH}_2$	0.0131	0.0130	0.0202	0.0203
	0.0425	0.0423	0.0340	0.0339
<i>o</i> -(CH_3) $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{NH}_2$	0.0206	0.0206	0.0153	0.0152
	0.0487	0.0485	0.0389	0.0388
<i>p</i> -(CH_3) $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{NH}_2$	0.0215	0.0215	0.0251	0.0251
	0.0447	0.0447	0.0406	0.0408
<i>o</i> -(OCH_3) $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{NH}_2$	0.0190	0.0189	0.0288	0.0288
	0.0398	0.0387	0.0400	0.0398
<i>p</i> -(OCH_3) $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{NH}_2$	0.0191	0.0189	0.0148	0.0148
	0.0302	0.0303	0.0403	0.0401
<i>o</i> -(OC_2H_5) $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{NH}_2$	0.0192	0.0191	0.0159	0.0158
	0.0402	0.0400	0.0452	0.0450
<i>p</i> -(OC_2H_5) $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{NH}_2$	0.0198	0.0198	0.0193	0.0192
	0.0398	0.0397	0.0447	0.0445

FIG. 1. Curves A to I represent respectively, *o*-ethoxyphenyl, *o*-tolyl, *p*-tolyl, *p*-methoxyphenyl, *p*-ethoxyphenyl, *o*-methoxyphenyl-thioureas, thiourea, *n*-butyl- and methyl-thioureas.

The results recorded above show that the listed compounds can be determined by titration with standard (*N/20*) iodine monochloride solution. Thiourea and its organic derivatives are oxidised by iodine monochloride to their corresponding disulphides.

(R = alkyl or aryl group).

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
PANJAB UNIVERSITY,
CHANDIGARH.

Received November 26, 1961.